

The Impact of Ethical Leadership & Civility on Organizational Commitment: The Mediating Role of Work Engagement

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ABSTRACT

Purpose – This paper holds the purpose to investigate the impact of ethical leadership and civility on organizational commitment and also to explore mediating role of work engagement in the relationship.

Design/methodology/approach – With questionnaire survey, the current paper uses a sample of 340 employees from manufacturing sector of Lahore Pakistan.

To test the hypotheses, analysis was accomplished by using Statistical Package for Social Science Software, through confirmatory factor and regression analysis. Findings – The results revealed that ethical leadership and civility have positive impact on organizational commitment. Strong empirical support also proved that work engagement mediates the relationship between ethical leadership, civility and organizational commitment.

Research limitations/implications – This study design is cross-sectional, consequently accuracy of assumption concerning causality is restrictive. Practical implications – Results of this study discovered the importance of ethical leadership behaviors which play noteworthy role in developing employees and ethical organizational culture & support to ascertain an organizational ethical environment that leads to maximize work engagement and organizational commitment. Thus, ethical leadership behaviors & civility might be the key and most suitable practices to be implemented in manufacturing sector of Pakistan.

Originality/value – This paper adds to the existing ethical leadership and civility literature by identifying work engagement as an additional mediator in the relationship between ethical leadership, civility and organizational commitment

Introduction

Association among leader's good ability and commitment in the sector of Jordan banks was examined by (Abuzaid, 2018). This study contributes much towards literature and pointed that ethical leadership is key factor that settle the organizational commitment (Ahmad & Gao, 2018). Ethical leadership believes about long term results and related benefits for the employees as well as for organizations because ethical leaders restrained ethical behaviors (Brown et al, 2006). EL add to organizational commitment. It also has positive outcomes of employee's towards work related behaviors and attitude. As this paper adds to existing literature but some of the process stay put. Firstly, this study is being carried out in banks of Jordan. So, the results cannot imitate to other industry and or sector. Secondly, research is made on precise administration rank of a particular industry. Therefore, due to the changing demographics and increasing challenges, morality of ethical leadership and civility is required to be fulfilled. Relations side by decent ability aspiration followers, consequences should be vigorously discovered.

Scholar like Iverson et al. (2011) recommended that ethical leadership may have different connotations in diverse states. For organizational success in challenging environment, it is beneficial and vital to inspect ethical leadership effects on employee's work engagement in other states like Pakistan. Therefore, the present research is a thrust to glance the impact of ethical values on solid liability with intervene employee work engagement in

manufacturing region of Lahore, Pakistan. To fill the proposed gap in ethical leadership, work engagement, organizational commitment and civility, this study is attempt for realistic privileged for long run and generation of ethical place of work where employees are treated in decent way with respect and dignity. It is projected that work engagement could likewise be merge as between mediator in model to evaluate ethical leadership and civility impact on employee commitment towards organization in various situations.

Despite of the various positive benefits and outcome of ethical leadership on staff behavior, still there is a need to inspect the employee's commitment as an important indicator towards organization's success (Kuh, Kinzie, Buckley, Bridges & Hayek, 2011). Civility which holds significant benefits in terms of employee behavior grasp a very minor intention (Demirtas et al, 2015), mainly in non-western countries for good performance of organizations (Halbesleben, 2010). From last few decades, manufacturing industries especially footwear business has gained a major role in the economy development of Pakistan. The industry of footwear is gaining its importance due to the quickly shifting environment and soaring expectations of customers.

Being a major concern for the development of Pakistan's economy, footwear industry is facing challenging difficulties in term of profit, high turnover of trained employees due to the fact of less commitment towards organization, unethical behavior and less engaged workforce. For future challenge and cover up the current issues successfully, without taking into account ethical standards and civility, organizational commitment is not possible to understand appropriately. The challenging situation describe for research to discriminate the factors that could upgrade organizational commitment of employees in Footwear business of Pakistan. Ethical leadership, work engagement and civility be key factors to enhance commitment towards organization.

Currently organizational commitment and ethical leadership are the important point of view that links efforts to argue in the focal point of market. Organizations who have engaged employees make a significant contribution towards organization's success for long run (Ahmad & Gao, 2018). Human, being an important part of the organization cannot be ignored in term of satisfaction, engagement, happy and contented because these reasonably affect organizational commitment, and without these employees are not put forward towards job in positive way to achieve organizational commitment. The current effort established ethical approach and civility are the key factors that realize committed, provoked and satisfied workers. As compared to other authoritative styles, ethical leadership has gotten worth mentioning appeal to scholars of administration business.

The current analysis provides the rational of ethical leadership that proceed desired work-related results which consist of satisfaction of job, engagement in work & organizational commitment and reduce turnover intention and deviance manner of workers (Hoch, Bommer, Dulebohn, & Wu 2018). There is a huge accord in the business of manufacturing of Pakistan from last decade, because this business has made a lot growth and employment opportunities in various zones. Manufacturing business has a lot potential in expression of finance, growth and development of the country, so it is important that manufacturing trade be developed and progressive and this is only possible by elite necessities ethical leaders, dedicated and standards of respect and ethics. Different perspectives stimulate ethical leadership and organization's representative's responsibility. However, ethical leadership & civility, effects organizational commitment mediating relationship of work engagement in manufacturing division of Lahore, Pakistan is explored in the current case.

Theoretical Perspective & Hypothesis

Ethical Leadership & Work Engagement

On the basis of moral decision, leaders of beliefs conduct in a principled manner both in terms of personally and professionally. This act of morality displays these leaders as a representative for their followers. Expansion of ethical plan is experienced as of other administrative construct and provides regular difference in a range of work-related outcomes relating to employees (Ng & Feldman, 2015). It is indicated by (Ahmad & Gao, 2018) that leaders of ethic illustrate moral conduct as an individual and manager. Moral individual, describe through legitimacy, integrity & loyalty, whereas ethical manager depicts to settle balanced decisions and used options, utter demands of job that linked with mission and objectives of organizations and show care for employees. Employees feel more engaged and committed when they receive moral conduct from their employers (Leiter et al, 2011 & Lee, 2011). Models of ethical leadership suggested moral leaders confer major way that deals to employees from top to bottom (Schwartz, 2016). It is worth mentioning that currently all organizations and business emerge to loyalty one of the important qualities in potential representatives (Dimitriou, 2016).

Cho et al., (2018) define work engagement "constructive motivating and psychological business-related

position with three measurements: energy, commitment, and incorporation". Force element involve ability to put tries in work. Loyalty judgment entails sense, self-importance, strength, inspiration, and face up to work, as integration gets the exclusivity of strong-minded and close liability in job. Accountability of work stimulate motivation and wake up constructive attitude in employees to organization (Chen and Kao, 2012). Obligations in job emphasize an unusual condition energy, insertion, and sense of duty (Demirtas, 2015). (Brandebo et al., 2016) indicated that engaged workforce are tend to be more energetic, dedicated and concentrated towards their work and organization

JD-R; Bakker (2017), the Demands-Resources theory of Job offers absolute characteristics of job theory along with an intention to clarify culture of organization and practices of management in either terms that is poor health and motivation at work. According to Demands-Resources theory of Job, resources are connected with occupation comprise physical, societal, psychological and administrative circumstances in which employees be inclined to carry out allotted jobs, which are equipped in advance the organizational objective and reducing the work demands, that support for individual development and growth. On the basis of beforehand state information, first hypothesis is projected as pursues:

H1: Ethical Leadership is positively associated to Work Engagement.

Work Engagement & Organizational Commitment

Commitment toward work, firstly developed by Kahn (1990) as of "individual commitment. It indicated that "organizational commitment is characterized "a helpful, pleasing, business linked viewpoint that is explained by life, attachment, and preservation" (Schaufeli et al., 2002, p. 74). It is described by Salanova et al., (2005) that work commitment has three dimensions: existence, loyalty, and ingestion. Vigor is to express the ability of growing in a working environment associated complication". Commitment articulates "motivation, accomplishment, force, and the declaration to strike the complexity break up away". Absorption reproduces "being pleased and balanced on work to the degree that delegate practice difficulty even as separating from work". (Vassos et al., 2017; Geldenhuys et al., 2014) explain power, obligation, & integration by three schemes of commitment of job represent the physical, zealous, & rational highlights.

Employees who are committed produce useful results for organization in term of time, energy and obligation as those who are increasingly coupled have striking level of strength and psychological completion. The reality has been paid by the writers that essence of dissimilarity about commitment at work b/w a leader a necessary part of circumstances where employees working, their characteristic and process is observed to perform (Bakker et al., 2014).

The basis of commitment was provided by (Kahn, 1990). Commitment as an expression being converse from past decades, however many researchers in the field of psychology, business management endeavor to re-arrange this as per a variety of dimensions, still a clear definition is required due to changeable business requisites. According to Kahn, (1990), work commitment is related to intellectual and physical activities that put on their action while employees are performing their assigned jobs. Employees who are committed towards organizations are expressed themselves physically (actually), emotionally (expressively) and cognitively (intuition) attached which shows from their performances (Kahn, 1990). Macey and Schneider (2008) described work commitment is directly connected to business success that deal with functional, rewarding and inspiring point of view. It is suggested by Bakker, and Albrecht (2018). Bakker and Leiter (2010) that the more associated and linked employee's produce good results for organization at significant level because they put their energy and mental fulfillment that support them to be more centered with their activity.

Additionally, González-Romá et al (2006) outline work commitment with three capacity as energy, devotion and absorption (whole attention). Vigor speaks as strong level of energy and metal state when working. Commitment (devotion) is connected through dedication and loyalty, while inclusion is reproducing as a noteworthy attention (González-Romá et al, 2006). As per the significance that basically related for organizational execution, commitment at work has extensive ever more map in the ground of reliable behavior, and productive hierarchical contribution (Macey, Schneider, Barbera, and Young, 2009). Based on the previously mentioned data, second investigation is anticipated as follows:

H2: Work engagement is positively related to Organizational commitment.

Ethical Leadership & Organizational Commitment

Gatling et al., (2016) demonstrated a strong link b/w good leader and employee's attitude who are responsible for organizational success and commitment. Meaning that when leaders of ethics cares about employees, they lean to see reasonable conduct from employer. In return workers put their best to meet the organizational goals & have encouraging attitude and commitment towards organization (Ployhart, 2006) and career (Parker et al, 2011) & convincing requirements (Tims et al., 2010). Leader's behavior is directly allied to staff commitment and satisfaction in job & addresses the related issues (Griffin & Guez, 2014). Accordingly, it deserves inspection to know the reasons how leaders start the environment of ethics that impact motivation at work, development and responsibility of implementation.

In many writings, results of leader's styles and related benefits have been shown (Zazou et al., 2019; Peng & Lin 2017). Due to the culture range and differences, not more assessment had been conducted that recognized leader's liability to business. It is suggested by Zhu et al., (2004) to have leaders of ethics which have important and positive outcome of moral scheme. This author paid attention on the positive consequences of ethical leadership on behavior of employees. Trevino et al., (2003) advised that loyal administrative reform add value and success to organization set up. Leader's moral behavior has direct and indirect impact on employee's attitude in terms of satisfaction and commitment towards association (Pettijohn et al. 2008). Employment factors that matter as fulfillment or turnover are subjected to moral conduct. A link b/w proper manner & touching dependability been revealed by (Veitch, Raymond, Farr, Farr, Graff, Vitale, & Wade, 2015). Obviously, many researchers measured involvement between respect basing, authoritative and transformational supervision. It has been found in much analysis similar to (Gulluce et al. 2016; Shim & Stephens 2015; Feizi et al. 2014), productive correspondence between transformational and other leadership styles. In light of the above information, the second assessment is imparted as seeks after:

H3: Ethical leadership is positively associated to organizational commitment.

Work Engagement as Mediator between Ethical Leadership & Organizational Commitment

On the foundation supposed model, we have implied that WE mediator between ethical leadership, civility and organizational commitment. Moral leaders give co-workers self-rule and supervise accomplishment that offer inference for their self-reliance (Luthans, F. 2003). It paves ways for ultimate success of organization (Lu et al, 2014). Responsibility at work is being seen like a vast inspiring source that engages employees to be extra vigorously committed with their association (Porath et al, 2012). Stander & Rothmann, (2010); Bhatnagar et al, (2012), engaged employees apply larger vigor and vigorously involved in their tasks and work. Accumulating, it is asserted that right direction will promote worker s' work commitment, which improve their OC. Thus, we put forward that:

H4: Work engagement mediates relationship between Ethical Leadership and Organizational commitment.

Civility & Work Engagement

Cornell, (2013) identified civility as prescribed interpersonal actions that verified value and be in love with others to create useful affairs at work place (p. 33). It is further elaborated by Pearson et al, (1999) as "the relationship of respect between people. Civility /incivility being different in nature, tendency may be common for utilization of ethics at work environment. Rude or ill-mannered behavior from leaders and or managers that shortfall regard and admiration to others falls as uncivil attitude. Impolite reasoned for damaging the level of respect at place of work (Andersson & Pearson, 1999). Due to that reason, it creates harmful results for employee and for organization like deviant behavior, abusive direction etc. Uncivil behavior spoils the workplace standards, while civility or civil actions support and help the moral principles and values of the organization as it is measured as remedy for harmful belief towards human and organization (Pearson & Rohwer, 2000). It is very important for the organizational success that ethical norms be impended in true letter and spirit. Civil behavior being a vital but overlooked attention towards success of an organization because it fortifies the control of manager or leader moral attitude for the organizational commitment, who contribute hard work, time & vigor to associations. Civility is a significant facet and input for performance & commitment of organization, which provide basics for positive outcomes, support to employees and supervisors for improved organizational operations.

Kahn (1990) commence work or employee engagement which tie up together members of organization who are physically, psychologically and thoughtfully engaged themselves to their role and organization for better performance for long term. Authors like Rich, LePine & Crawford, (2010) highlighted that individual who is more engaged can face stress with support and enthusiasm in an environment of civility. Despite of the fact that world admit importance of work engagement, yet it entails more emphasis to know about disengagement of employees.

Due to regional limitations, only 33% of US employees are engaged whereas rest of the world is at back end which indicates work engagement importance. According to Gallup, (2017) percentages in other countries like Western Europe and Eastern Europe are 10 % and 15 % respectively. Still root cause resides unrevealed, research have discovered that if ethical leadership style takes into account and considered for ultimate organizational outcomes, then possibilities are there for making workforce more engaged at workplace.

H5: Civility is positively related to Work engagement.

Civility & Organizational Commitment

Achieve competitive sustainable advantage in changing work demands, recognizing one's efforts, attention of being care, and improvement in personal & professional caliber are necessity of the present century. Civility is being often unnoticed problem deal within work-place (Glass et al., 2013; Roberts & Ayre, 2002). In workplace, incivility being an important rationale of turnover (Fouad et al, 2011), which have different negative consequences on the behavior of people and push them to leave jobs. It is very significant to identify factors that precede deliberation & offer effort that control workplace incivility and encourage organizational commitment (Thomas, Bystydzienski, & Desai, 2015). Leiter et al., (2011) indicated that treatment of employees psychologically is planned attempt that leads set up employees for job demands, reduce incivility and attain organizational commitment. It is also argued that civility encourage employees for helpful and careful behavior to others which establishes good working relations (Cajaiba-Santana, 2014).

Giroto et al, (2013) emphasized that according to present state of doing business, everything has changed i.e., structure, administration by the means of HR practices. Organizations that set strong connection with workers through a culture of ethics and civility, leads and effect behavior and association of employees for organizational commitment. Respectful working atmosphere develop and promote engaged & committed workers who are always ready to respond to job demands with more responsibility and energy. Based on the previous research, for corporate world & industry executives, this study expectation positively helpful to develop & promote culture of ethic that decrease rude behavior and unethical practices. Employees receive an environment of respect from employer and react with greater zeal and trust. Civil working environment employee's work engagement, retention of skilled human capital increases which leads to increase organizational commitment; accordingly, 6th investigation hypothesis is proposed as follows:

H6: Civility is positively associated to Organizational commitment

Mediating role of Work engagement in between Civility & Organizational Commitment

Civil behavior, being an important factor of working environment effects employee's outcomes in workplace (Ahmad & Gao,2018; Abuzaid, 2018) In human psychology and organizational behavior, description of civility is in the course of good manners, politeness, respect, and as a whole response to the other's rights, which smooth ways for competitive sustainable advantage (Lee et al, 2011). When organization develops and promote civil working environment, employees experience more confident and valued in association that leads to organizational commitment. It is important to mentioned that organizational commitment is directly associated to employee's attachment with organization (Wombacher & Felfe, 2017). Being civil or civility in organization means arrangements of respect, honesty, trust, and careful behavior with others at working place (Abdallah et al., 2014). Civility generates good and harmonious relationship between individuals that effect employee's psychology and they feel pleasant and being respected which in turn create and maintain their engagement at work (Duggan, 2014; Duggan,2017). Employees when valued and respected vigorously distribute more responsibility, engagement and commitment towards their job responsibilities that promote organizational commitment (Smittick, Miner, & Miner, 2018). Conversely, civility is a significant trait for organizational commitment is ignored and understudied (Glass et al., 2013). Hence, we suggest that:

H7: Work Engagement mediates relationship between civility and organizational commitment.

Figure 1

Method

Sample and Procedure

Study was conducted in shoe manufacturing sector. The population hold employees of shoe manufacturing, located at Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan. Quantitative research method used for current study. Technique which was used to collect data is stratified random sampling technique. Questionnaire survey used as an instrument for collection of data. Total 400 questionnaire survey were distributed among the serving employees of shoe manufacturing in which 340 (85%) usable questionnaires were received. 40 (10%) respondents did not return the questionnaire whereas 20 (5%) respondents returned incomplete questionnaire.

Out of 340 respondents, 299 were male and 41 were female yielding the percentages of 88% and 12 % respectively. 134 (37%) respondents fall in the pay scale 1-7 were in majority. Most of respondents 107 (32%) fall in the age group of 20-30. Respondents 146 (43%) having the experience of 5 years. Respondents 238 were married and 102 were unmarried which presents the percentage of 70% and 30 % respectively.

Measures

All the measures were adopted and measured on five-point Likert scales ranging from 1-5 (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree & Strongly Disagree). The variables of this study are Ethical leadership, civility, work engagement and organizational commitment. These measures were adopted and measured on 5-point likert scale. **Ethical Leadership.** This scale was ten items and developed by (Brown et al, 2005). An example item was “My supervisor can be trusted”. Reliability of the measure was 0.927. **Civility.** Porath and Erez, (2009), four-item scale, civility was used. Example item was “Do your co-workers treat you in a polite manner? Reliability of the measure was found 0.856. **Work Engagement.** Schaufeli et al., (2006), work engagement scale was used with nine items. Sample item was “I feel happy when I am working intensely”. Reliability of the measure was 0.818. **Organizational Commitment.** Alan M. Saks (2006), Organizational commitment was measured with six items. Sample item was “I am proud to tell others I work at my organization”. Reliability was found 0.929.

Control Variables

Control variable which was used in the study included age, gender, pay scale, experience and marital status. These variables were not included in theoretical model but influence the results. Data of these variables were collected with study variables.

Data Analysis Approach

Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS 24) were used for descriptive analysis which included frequencies, mean, standard deviation and correlation. Hypotheses were tested by using PROCESS macros (Hayes,

& Preacher, 2013). The study holds two mediation models, as two independent variables are involved in the theoretical framework (Figure-1). Model-1 examined hypothesis H1 & H4 and mediation model-2 model analyzed the hypothesis H5 & H7. Measurement model was examined by using Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS 24).

Findings

Descriptive Analysis

Study variables (ethical leadership, civility, work engagement and organizational commitment) mean, standard deviation & correlation includes, in addition to control variables (age, gender, pay scale, qualification, experience and marital status) was shown in Table-1. Scales reliabilities sorted from 0.82 to 0.96, which is reliable with hypothesized model.

Results showed that ethical leadership is positively and significantly related to work engagement ($r= 0.665$, $P<0.01$), and organizational commitment ($r= 0.618$, $P<0.01$). Civility is positively and significantly related to work engagement ($r= 0.595$, $P<0.01$), and organizational commitment ($r= 0.625$, $P<0.01$). Results also indicate that work engagement is positively related to organizational commitment ($r=0.673$, $P< 0.01$). Correlation analysis gives the primary support to our hypothesized model.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 1. Correlations

Variables	Mean	S. D	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Gender	1.12	.326	1								
2. Pay Scale	1.83	.768	-.130*	1							
3. Age	2.31	1.136	-.286**	.342**	1						
4. Experience	2.49	1.776	-.281**	.256**	.770**	1					
5. Marital Status	1.30	.459	.388**	-.248**	-.595**	-.446**	1				
6. Ethical Leadership	3.10	.867	-.138*	-.050	-.037	.118*	.002	1			
7. Work Engagement	3.53	.573	-.192**	.143**	.001	.163**	-.095	.665**	1		
8. Civility	3.61	.762	-.114*	.136*	.024	.153**	-.087	.583**	.595**	1	
9. Organizational Commitment	3.53	.889	-.145**	.067	.051	.185**	-.070	.618**	.673**	.625**	1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Andrew F Hayes's PROCESS Macro model 4 (Hayes & Preacher, 2013) was used to check the study hypothesis. Results of hypothesis testing have shown in table 2 and 3. Results of SPSS PROCESS macro specified that ethical leadership significantly impact work engagement ($\beta=0.440$, $t=16.353$, $p<0.000$), hence H1 is supported ("a" path of figure 2). Work engagement has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment ($\beta=0.730$, $t=9.174$, $p<0.000$), when controlling for ethical leadership (path "b" of figure 2). Ethical leadership has a positive and significant impact on organizational commitment ($\beta=0.313$, $t=5.942$, $p<0.000$),

While controlling for work engagement (c` path in figure 2), these outcomes supported H2 and H4. Findings indicated too that total effect of ethical leadership on organizational commitment was positive and significant ($\beta=0.643$, $t=14.434$, $p<0.000$), so supported H3 (c path in figure 2).

Findings of simple mediation model suggested that ethical leadership has an indirect effect on organizational commitment through work engagement. The indirect effect was ($\beta=0.321$) and two tailed significance for normal distribution showed that indirect effect was significant (Sobel $z=7.990$, $p<0.001$). The bootstrap results consistent with Sobel 95% CI (0.721, 0.398) around indirect effect (ab) have a non-zero point. Thus, H4 was supported.

Moreover, the results indicated that civility positively impact work engagement ($\beta=0.448$, $t=13.613$, $p<0.000$), thus H5 is supported (path "a" in Figure 3). Work engagement positively impact organizational commitment ($\beta=0.723$, $t=10.047$, $p<0.000$), while controlling for civility (path "b" in Figure 3). Civility has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment ($\beta=0.406$, $t=7.490$, $p<0.000$), when controlling for

work engagement (c` path in figure 3). In line with H6, results confirmed that total effect of civility on organizational commitment (c path in Figure 3) was positive and significant ($\beta=0.729$, $t=14.723$, $p<0.000$). Lastly, to support our H7, results indicated that indirect association between civility and organizational commitment was positive ($\beta=0.324$) and significant (Sobel $z= 8.070$, $p< 0.001$). The bootstrap result verified Sobel test because 95% confidence interval (CI .257, .387) around indirect effect (ab) did not hold zero. Hence, H7 was supported.

Table 2. Results of Simple Mediation Model

Variables	B	SE	t	P		
Direct and Total Effect						
Organizational commitment regressed on EL	0.634	0.044	14.434	0.000		
Work engagement regressed on EL	0.440	0.027	16.353	0.000		
Organizational commitment regressed on work engagement controlling EL	0.730	0.080	9.174	0.000		
Organizational commitment regressed on EL controlling work engagement	0.313	0.053	5.942	0.000		
	Value	SE	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI	Z	P
Indirect effect and significance using the normal distribution						
Sobel	0.324	0.040	.271	.398	8.070	0.000
	ME	SE	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI	Z	P
Bootstrap results for indirect effect						
Effect	0.324	0.040	.271	.398	8.070	0.000

Note: N = 340. β = Unstandardized Regression Coefficient; SE = Standard Error; Bootstrap Sample Size = 1000;

LL = Lower Limit; CI = Confidence Interval; UL = Upper Limit, 1,000 Bootstrapping

Table 2. Results of Simple Mediation Model

Variables	B	SE	t	P		
Direct and Total Effect						
Organizational commitment regressed on civility	0.729	0.050	14.723	0.000		
Work engagement regressed on civility	0.448	0.033	13.613	0.000		
Organizational commitment regressed on work engagement controlling Civility	0.723	0.072	10.047	0.000		
Organizational commitment regressed on civility controlling work engagement	0.406	0.054	7.490	0.000		
	Value	SE	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI	Z	P
Indirect effect and significance using the normal distribution						
Sobel	0.321	0.040	.257	.387	7.990	0.000
	ME	SE	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI	Z	P
Bootstrap results for indirect effect						
Effect	0.321	0.040	.257	.387	7.990	0.000

Note: N = 340. β = Unstandardized Regression Coefficient; SE = Standard Error; Bootstrap Sample Size = 1000;

LL = Lower Limit; CI = Confidence Interval; UL = Upper Limit, 1,000 Bootstrapping

Figure 2

Figure 3

Discussion

Current research adds to prevailing literature through empirically examining backgrounds and results of ethical leadership. Particularly, the current study is an exclusive effort to examine ethical leadership, work civility as history of work engagement & organizational commitment as consequence in Pakistan perspective. It is first attempt which examines direct impact of ethical leadership, civility on work engagement & organizational commitment, investigates mediating role of work engagement between ethical leadership, organizational commitment & also between civility, organizational commitment in shoe manufacturing area of Lahore, Pakistan. Results support our hypothesized model. This study holds seven main results which are conferred below:

At first, research revealed that EL is absolutely & significantly associated to work engagement. Brown et al, (2005) Ethical leadership acts vital part in serving, shaping organization and motivation of employees through two-way communication as a moral manager Ethical leadership conduct provides as impacting motivational force behind employee’s behavior and attitude as a moral person (Brown and Trevino, 2006; McKay, Kuntz, & Näswall

2013), and it gives advantage to employees for accomplishment of personal and organizational goals and establish effective functioning to organization.

Second, study results demonstrated work engagement is absolutely associated to organizational commitment. If employees are more engaged in their work, they will devote more efforts towards their job and organization. Employees could experience to respond with engagement level, if organization provide work environment that is resourceful as well as job resources like feedback, support, and information, which contribute to work engagement Breevaart et al., (2014) that leads to organizational commitment. Study results empirically supports that work engagement is important that visualize organizational commitment of employees.

Third, our findings confirmed ethical leadership & organizational commitment are positively related. Ethical leaders focus on fair treatment of others and establish work environment that is supportive and encourage normatively suitable behavior (Brown et al, 2005). Ethical leadership is crucial factor that manipulate the work environment and how employees recognize their work (Christian, Garza, & Slaughter, 2011) and organization, because leaders improve employee organizational commitment, as if employees are satisfy with their work atmosphere & leaders be more committed to organization.

Fourthly, work engagement mediates relationship b/w ethical leadership and organizational commitment. Employees optimally engaged in their work and job tasks, they tend to be more committed toward organization as they knew that leaders of the organization are supportive, helping and improves their work performance for accomplishment of personal as well as organizational goals. A visible and established working environment based on trust and ethics is more to allow employees with approach of psychological possession and commitment toward the workplace (Avey et al., 2012).

Fifth, results of our study discovered that being civil is certainly related to work engagement. Humble environment is significant factor for success of organization in today's growing world. Civil work atmosphere is crucial for improvement and survival of organizations. At work, civility encourages employee's energy which they get from their supervisors/leaders and enhance their motivation and work engagement. Moreover, conclusions empirically demonstrated employee's feel more motivated and passionate as receive dutiful conduct at work (Heymann, Gross, Tabenkin, Porter, & Porath, 2011; Reio & Ghosh, 2009).

Finally, research found work engagement mediates association between civility & organizational commitment. Politeness establishes helpful moods in relative to other employees. In an organization civility work environment, individuals feel a sense of being requested which creates energetic work environment that proves work engagement in work (Pearson & Porter, 2009), while employees engaged in job, promote concentration in job actions developed more involved & committed to organization.

Theoretical Contribution

Present research contributed to literature of ethical leadership in many ways. By examining the antecedents and outcomes of ethical leadership contribute to existing literature. Past research focused on the consequences and behaviors elements of ethical leadership (Brown, Trevino et al, 2014). Correspondently, by these calls, the current study investigates the ethical leadership and civility as contributors, work engagement and organizational commitment as its outcomes. Finding of the study give sustenance to idea that ethical leadership & civility work environment promote employee's energy which they get from their leaders, supervisors enhance motivational & eagerness workplace.

Second, results validated constructive association between work engagement and organizational commitment empirically; it proved on beneficial results of ethical leadership at workplace suggested by different researchers (Toor and Ofori, G. 2009). Employees engaged in their work activities when they feel motivated and supportive by their leaders and organization in such a way employee because more occupied in tasks (Wallace et al, 2017). Thirdly, research explored mediating role of work engagement between ethical leadership and organizational commitment & also between civility and organizational commitment to clarify why & how employees engaged and committed at workplace.

Fourth, ethical leadership & organizational commitment relationship also between civility and organizational commitment are revealed and confirmed empirically in the organizational context. If organization involved in establishment and development of ethical standards values based on trust and respect at work environment, the more employees will be engaged and committed to organization (Yaoa et al., 2019). Additionally,

when employees get civil behaviors at work environment and from subordinates, it automatically motivates them for more engaged in job duties (Yu et al., 2019).

Practical Contributions

The current investigation gives significant suggestions for leaders & experts. It detected that ethical leadership & civility are imperative interpreters of work engagement & organizational commitment. Jointly, ethical leadership and civility was positively & significantly impact on work engagement and organizational commitment in manufacturing sector. Work environment is rapidly changing due to today's growing needs and responsiveness around job matters. The current inquiry suggested leaders of manufacturing segment could enhance work engagement, organizational commitment employees by promoting civil and ethical behavior in the organization. In civil, ethical occupied organizations, workers impression psychological satisfied and more motivated toward their job tasks and as well as toward organization. Employees feel greater sense of wish to feel dedicated, engaged in job & achieve organizational objectives and aims. This examination gives important implications to human resource department consultants and HR supervisors in the development of employment policies. Management of the organization should indirect individuals who possess civil and respectful behaviors and wish to extend their efforts to others for desired work outcomes.

Moreover, the current study implies that whenever employees and work in an environment that is based on civility, they tend to feel more engaged satisfied which increase their engagement in job duties and commitment to organization. Principally, there is dare need for organization to promote ethical leadership and civility at work for development of productive work environment for work engagement and organizational commitment. Management can provide civil environment through training of employees for uncivil behaviors and ethical leadership can promote by development of ethical leadership who are capable enough to shape the organization culture in true leaders as a moral person and moral manager.

Furthermore, civility positive work environment results in beneficial outcomes like work engagement and organizational commitment. There is a need for organization to evaluate the employee's ethical considerations and values their respect at workplace and towards other and try to enhance organizational resources that encourage it. For that sake, management should indirect ways to develop it. These interferences focused on promoting choice of decision making, work engagement knowledge acquire and sharing and responsive to civil environment (Porter et al, 2008). Organizations based on shared values of respect civility establish a positive work environment that effect individual's behaviors to jointly support each other's at work place.

Additionally, this research provides various ideas for SHRM & HRD professionals and practitioners. Professional of human resource department should create training program on civility and ethical values and train employees about the values of civil behaviors at work place. SHRM professionals & practitioners should inspire managers and leaders regarding importance of ethical values and civil behaviors and should engage in developing image of the organization. Consequently, employees could be motivated to get high level of engagement and commitment to organization.

Limitations and Future Scope

This study makes a new effort to inspect the effect of ethical leadership and civility on commitment of organization using mediating role of work engagement and build exclusive contributions to ethical leadership literature. The current research is not without limitations, which offer capacity for future research studies.

First, primary data gather through sole cause i.e., from serving workers/staff, might result biasness and study association may be limited. Second, in this research, we inspect consequence of ethical guidance and Civility on OC (organizational commitment) via interceding influence engagement at work through study design cross sectional. Such plan could not resolve the cause-and-effect relationship between study variables, therefore future research could explore the relationship by using design of longitudinal study.

Thirdly, is data of present examination is collected from manufacturing sector of Lahore Pakistan by using stratified random sampling. Findings may not be the accurate functioning in other sectors /cities of Pakistan. For the purpose of generalizability, future researchers could take data from other sectors and cities of Pakistan.

Fourth part, the present study investigates impact ethical leadership & civility on organizational commitment through work engagement and principally accomplished in the work situation of Pakistani contexts. Studies for future could validate results of this study in other developed countries as (Choi et al., 2015) indicated

that culture and work procedures of Pakistan are diverse from other developing regions.

Fifth, in this study, we inspected WE as a single mediator between EL and OC and between civility and OC. Future researcher can have the opportunity to explore other mediators, for example, JS, OC self-efficacy, self-esteem etc.

Conclusion

Present study endorses important contribution to EL literature through examining the antecedents and outcomes empirically in manufacturing sector of Pakistan. Findings tested empirically confirmed significant and positive connection of proposed relationships. This study also revealed that work engagement mediates relationship between EL and OC & between civility and OC also. It indicates EL and courtesy at workplace play crucial role in effecting the employee's engagement and commitment towards work. Consequently, organizations must emphasis on establish a respectful and civil environment and on development of EL to promote employee's work engagement and organizational commitment in today's demanding organizational requirements.

References

- Abdallah, A. B., Obeidat, B. Y., & Aqqad, N. O. (2014). The impact of supply chain management practices on supply chain performance in Jordan: The moderating effect of competitive intensity. *International Business Research*, 7(3), 13.
- Abuzaid, A. N. (2018). The relationship between ethical leadership and organizational commitment in banking sector of Jordan. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, © Emerald Publishing Limited, 1026-4116. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEAS-01-2018-0006>
- Ahmad, I., & Gao, Y. (2018). Ethical leadership and work engagement. *Management Decision*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-02-2017-0107>
- Andersson, L. M., & Pearson, C. M. (1999). Tit for tat? The spiraling effect of incivility in the workforce. *Academy of Management Review*, 24(3), 452—471. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/259136>
- Avey, J. B., Wernsing, T. S., & Palanski, M. E. (2012). Exploring the process of ethical leadership: The mediating role of employee voice and psychological ownership. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 107(1), 21-34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1298-2>
- Bakker, A. B., & Leiter, M. P. (Eds.). (2010). *Work engagement: A handbook of essential theory and research*. Psychology press.
- Bakker, A.B. (2017). Strategic and proactive approaches to work engagement. *Organizational Dynamics*, 46, 67-75. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2017.04.002>
- Bakker, A.B. and Demerouti, E. (2014). *Job demands-resources theory, in Chen, P.Y. and Cooper, C.L. (Eds), Wellbeing: A Complete Reference Guide, Vol. III*, Wiley-Blackwell, Chichester, 37-64.
- Bakker, A.B., Albrecht, S. (2018). Work engagement: current trends. *Career Development International*, 23(1), 4-11. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-11-2017-0207>
- Bhatnagar, J. (2012). Management of innovation: role of psychological empowerment, work engagement and turnover intention in the Indian context. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23(5), 928-951. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2012.651313>
- Brandebo, M.F., Nilsson, S. and Larsson, G. (2016). Leadership: is bad stronger than good? *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 37(6), 690-710. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-09-2014-0191>
- Breevaart, K., Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2014). Daily self-management and employee work engagement. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 84(1), 31-38.
- Brown, M. E., & Treviño, L. K. (2006). Ethical leadership: A review and future directions. *The Leadership Quarterly* 17, 595–616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2006.10.004>
- Brown, M. E., & Treviño, L. K. (2014). Do role models matter? An investigation of role modeling as an antecedent of perceived ethical leadership. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 122(4), 587-598.
- Brown, M.E., Treviño, L.K., & Harrison, D.A. (2005). Ethical leadership: A social learning perspective for construct development and testing. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 97,117–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2005.03.002>
- Cajaiba-Santana, G. (2014). Social innovation: Moving the field forward. A conceptual framework. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 82, 42-51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2013.05.008>
- Chen, C.-F. and Kao, Y.-L. (2012). Moderating effects of work engagement and job tenure on burnout – performance among flight attendants. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 25 (1), 61-63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jairtraman.2012.08.009>
- Cho, Y.H. and Lee, J.H. (2018). Entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurial education and performance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship* 12 (2), 124-134. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJIE-05-2018-0028>

- Choi, Y., & Chan, A. P. (2015). PROVEAN web server: a tool to predict the functional effect of amino acid substitutions and in dels. *Bioinformatics*, 31(16), 2745-2747.
- Christian, M.S., Garza, A.S., Slaughter, J.E. (2011). Work engagement: a quantitative review and test of its relations with task and contextual performance. *Personnel Psychology*, 64 (1), 89–136
- Cornell, S. (2013). Meaning and Understanding in the History of Constitutional Ideas: The Intellectual History Alternative to Originalism. *Fordham L. Rev.*, 82, 721. <https://ir.lawnet.fordham.edu/flr/vol82/iss2/12>
- Demerouti, E., Cropanzano, R., Bakker, A., & Leiter, M. (2010). From thought to action: Employee work engagement and job performance. *Work engagement: A handbook of essential theory and research*, 65(1), 147-163.
- Demirtas, O. (2015). Ethical leadership influence at organizations: evidence from the field. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 126(2), 273-284. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-013-1950-5>
- Devlin, J., Chang, M. W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2018). Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.04805*.
- Dimitriou, C. K. (2016). International hospitality companies. *Hospitality: An Introduction*, Kendall Hunt Publishing Company, Dubuque, IA, 123-134.
- Duggan, M., (2014). Online Harassment 2014. Technical Report. Pew Research Center, Washington, DC.
- Duggan, M., (2017). Online Harassment 2017. Technical Report. Pew Research Center.
- Feizi, M., Ebrahimi, E. and Beheshti, N. (2014). Investigating the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 3(1), 17-30.
- Fouad, N. A., Singh, R., Fitzpatrick, M. E., & Liu, J. P. (2011). Stemming the tide: Why women leave engineering. *University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee, Final report from NSF Award, 827553*.
- Gallup. (2017). *Gallup daily: U.S. employee engagement*. Retrieved from <https://news.gallup.com/poll/180404/gallup-dailyemployee-engagement.aspx>
- Gatling, A., Kang, H. J. A. & Kim, J. S. (2016). The effects of authentic leadership and organizational commitment on turnover intention. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 37(2), 181-199. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-05-2014-0090>
- Geldenhuis, M., Laba, K., & Venter, C. M. (2014). Meaningful work, work engagement and organisational commitment. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 40 (1), 01–10. <https://doi:10.4102/sajip.v40i1.1098>
- Giroto, E., Ceretta, C. A., Rossato, L. V., Farias, J. G., Tiecher, T. L., De Conti, L., & Nicoloso, F. T. (2013). Triggered antioxidant defense mechanism in maize grown in soil with accumulation of Cu and Zn due to intensive application of pig slurry. *Ecotoxicology and environmental safety*, 93, 145-155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2013.03.021>
- Glass, J. L., Sessler, S., Levitte, Y., & Micheltore, K. M. (2013). What’s so special about STEM? A comparison of women’s retention in STEM and professional occupations. *Social Forces*, 92 (2), 723–756. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1093%2Fsf%2Fsot092>
- González-Romá, V., Schaufeli, W. B., Bakker, A. B., & Lloret, S. (2006). Burnout and work engagement: Independent factors or opposite poles? *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 68 (1), 165–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2005.01.003>.
- Griffin, A. S., & Guez, D. (2014). Innovation and problem solving: a review of common mechanisms. *Behavioural Processes*, 109, 121-134.
- Griffin, M. A., Neal, A., & Parker, S. K. (2007). A new model of work role performance: Positive behavior in uncertain and interdependent contexts. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(2), 327–347. <https://doi:10.5465/amj.2007.24634438>
- Gulluce, A. Ç., Kaygin, E., Kafadar, S. B., & Atay, M. (2016). The relationship between transformational leadership and organizational commitment: A study on the bank employees. *Journal of Service Science and Management*, 9 (3), 263-275. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/jssm.2016.93033>
- Halbesleben, J. R. (2010). A meta-analysis of work engagement: Relationships with burnout, demands, resources, and consequences. *Work engagement: A handbook of essential theory and research*, 8(1), 102-117.
- Hayes, A. F., & Preacher, K. J. (2013). *Conditional process modeling: Using structural equation modeling to examine contingent causal processes*.
- Heymann, A. D., Gross, R., Tabenkin, H., Porter, B., & Porath, A. (2011). Factors associated with hypertensive patients' compliance with recommended lifestyle behaviors. *IMAJ-Israel Medical Association Journal*, 13(9), 553.
- Hoch, J. E., Bommer, W. H., Dulebohn, J. H., & Wu, D. (2018). Do ethical, authentic, and servant leadership explain variance above and beyond transformational leadership? A meta-analysis. *Journal of Management*, 44(2), 501-529. <https://doi:10.1177/0149206316665461>
- Israr Ahmad, I., & Gao, Y. (2018). Ethical leadership and work engagement: The roles of psychological empowerment and power distance orientation. *Management Decision*, 56(9), 1991-20. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-02-2017-0107>
- Iverson, K. M., Gradus, J. L., Resick, P. A., Suvak, M. K., Smith, K. F., & Monson, C. M. (2011). Cognitive–

- behavioral therapy for PTSD and depression symptoms reduces risk for future intimate partner violence among interpersonal trauma survivors. *Journal of consulting and clinical psychology*, 79(2), 193.
- Jada, U. R., Mukhopadhyay, S. (2019). Understanding the effects of empowering, transformational and ethical leadership on promotive and prohibitive voice A moderated mediated examination. *Personnel Review*, 48(3), 707-730. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-11-2017-0365>
- Jones, E. J., Costello, M. W., Schleiff, M., Miller, D. S., Chetal, A., Belden, M. M., & Gallup, V. V. (2017). *U.S. Patent No. 9,602,529*. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- Kahn, W.A. (1990). Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4), 692-724. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/256287>
- Kuh, G. D., Kinzie, J., Buckley, J. A., Bridges, B. K., & Hayek, J. C. (2011). *Piecing together the student success puzzle: Research, propositions, and recommendations*: ASHE higher education report (Vol. 116). John Wiley & Sons.
- Lee, S. S., Humphreys, K. L., Flory, K., Liu, R., & Glass, K. (2011). Prospective association of childhood attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and substance use and abuse/dependence: a meta-analytic review. *Clinical psychology review*, 31(3), 328-341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2011.01.006>
- Leiter, M. P., Day, A., Gilin-Oore, D., & Laschinger, H. (2012). Getting better and staying better: Assessing civility, incivility, distress and job attitudes one year after a civility intervention. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 17(4), 425–434. <https://doi:10.1037/a0029540>
- Leiter, M. P., Laschinger, H. K. S., Day, A., & Oore, D. G. (2011). The impact of civility interventions on employee social behavior, distress, and attitudes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 96 (6), 1258–1274. <https://doi:10.1037/a0024442>
- Lu, X., Wu, X., Wang, Y., Chen, H., Gao, P., & Fu, Y. (2014). Risk assessment of toxic metals in street dust from a medium-sized industrial city of China. *Ecotoxicology and environmental safety*, 106, 154-163.
- Luthans, F. (2003). *Positive organizational behavior: implications for leadership and HR development and motivation*. In: L. W. Porter, G. A. Bigley, & R. M. Steers (Eds.), *Motivation and work behavior*, (178–195), New York: McGraw-Hill/Irwin.
- Macey, W. H., & Schneider, B. (2008). The meaning of employee engagement. *Industrial and organizational Psychology*, 1(1), 3-30.
- Macey, W. H., Schneider, B., Barbera, K. M., & Young, S. A. (2009). Engaging engagement. *Employee Engagement: Tools for Analysis, Practice, and Competitive Advantage*, Wiley-Blackwell, Oxford, UK. <https://doi: 10.9781444306538>
- McKay, K., Kuntz, J. R., & Näswall, K. (2013). The effect of affective commitment, communication and participation on resistance to change: The role of change readiness. *New Zealand Journal of Psychology (Online)*, 42(2), 29.
- Muraro, A., Werfel, T., Hoffmann-Sommergruber, K., Roberts, G., Beyer, K., Bindslev-Jensen, C., & Fernandez Rivas, M. (2014). EAACI food allergy and anaphylaxis guidelines. diagnosis and management of food allergy. *Allergy*, 69(8), 1008-1025. <https://doi: 10.1111/all.12429>
- Ng, T.W.H. and Feldman, D.C. (2015). Ethical leadership: meta-analytic evidence of criterion-related and incremental validity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 100(3), 948-965. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0038246>
- Obeidat, B.Y., Masa, R.M.T. and Abdallah, B.A. (2014). The relationships among human resource management practices, Organizational commitment, and knowledge management processes: a structural equation modeling approach. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(3).
- Parker, S. K., & Griffin, M. A. (2011). Understanding active psychological states: Embedding engagement in a wider nomological net and closer attention to performance. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 20(1), 60-67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2010.532869>
- Pearson, C. M., & Porath, C. L. (2009). *The cost of bad behavior-how incivility damages your business and what you can do about it*. New York: Portfolio.
- Pearson, J. T., Noma, Y. A. S. U. H. I. R. O., & Tazawa, H. I. R. O. S. H. I. (1999). Developmental patterns of heart rate in altricial avian embryos and hatchlings. *Journal of experimental biology*, 202(11), 1545-1550.
- Pearson, S. F., & Rohwer, S. (2000). Asymmetries in male aggression across an avian hybrid zone. *Behavioral Ecology*, 11(1), 93-101.
- Peng, J. C., & Lin, J. (2017). Mediators of ethical leadership and group performance outcomes. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMP-10-2015-0370>
- Pettijohn, C., Pettijohn, L., & Taylor, A. J. (2008). Salesperson perceptions of ethical behaviors: Their influence on job satisfaction and turnover intentions. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 78(4), 547-557. <https://doi.10.1007/s10551-007-9367-7>
- Ployhart, R. E. (2006). Staffing in the 21st century: New challenges and strategic opportunities. *Journal of Management*, 32, 868–897. <https://doi.10.1177/0149206306293625>
- Poletta, F. A., Orioli, I. M., Mereb, J. C., Carvalho, F. M., Brandon, C. A., & Resick, J. M. (2011). A South American Cluster of Cleft Lip: Familial Relative Risks and Complex Segregation Analysis. *PLoS ONE*.

- Porath, C. L., & Erez, A. (2009). Overlooked but not untouched: How rudeness reduces onlookers' performance on routine and creative tasks. *Organizational Behavior & Human Decision Processes*, 109, 29–44. <https://doi:10.1016/j.obhdp.2009.01.003>
- Porath, C., Spreitzer, G., Gibson, C., & Garnett, F. G. (2012). Thriving at work: Toward its measurement, construct validation, and theoretical refinement. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 33(2), 250–275. <https://doi:10.1002/job.756>
- Porter, S. D. (2008). *Algal attributes: an autecological classification of algal taxa collected by the National Water-Quality Assessment Program*. Reston, VA: US Geological Survey.
- Reio Jr, T. G., & Ghosh, R. (2009). Antecedents and outcomes of workplace incivility: Implications for human resource development research and practice. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 20(3), 237-264.
- Rich, B. L., Lepine, J. A., & Crawford, E. E. (2010). Job engagement: Antecedents and effects on job performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53(3), 617–635. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25684339>
- Roberts, P., & Ayre, M. (2002). Did she jump or was she pushed? A study of women's retention in the engineering workforce. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, 18(4), 415-421.
- Saks, A. M. (2006). Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 21(7), 600-619. <https://doi:10.1108/02683940610690169>
- Salanova, M., Agut, S., & Peiró, J. M. (2005). Linking organizational resources and work engagement to employee performance and customer loyalty: The mediation of service climate. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90, 1217–1227. <https://doi:10.1037/0021-9010.90.6.1217>
- Schaufeli, W. B., Bakker, A. B., & Salanova, M. (2006). The measurement of work engagement with a short questionnaire: A cross-national study. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 66(4), 701-716. <https://doi:10.1177/0013164405282471>
- Schaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., González-Romá, V., & Bakker, A. B. (2002). The measurement of engagement and burnout: A two sample confirmatory factor analytic approach. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 3(1), 71–92.
- Schwartz, M. (2016). Ethical decision-making theory: an integrated approach. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 139(4), 755-776. <https://doi:10.1007/s10551-015-2886-8>
- Shim, H., & Stephens, M. (2015). Wavelet-based genetic association analysis of functional phenotypes arising from high-throughput sequencing assays. *The annals of applied statistics*, 9(2), 655.
- Smittick, A. L., Miner, K. N., & Cunningham, G. B. (2018). Sport Management Review. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smr.2018.06.002>
- Stander, M. W., & Rothmann, S. (2010). Psychological empowerment, job insecurity and employee engagement. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 36(1), 1-8. <https://doi:10.4102/sajip.v36i1.849>
- Thomas, N., Bystydzienski, J., & Desai, A. (2015). Changing institutional culture through peer mentoring of women STEM faculty. *Innovative Higher Education*, 40(2), 143-157. <https://doi:10.1007/s10755-014-9300-9>
- Tims, M., & Bakker, A. B. (2010). Job crafting: Towards a newmodel of individual job redesign. *South-African Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 36, 1–9. <https://doi:10.4102/sajip.v36i2.841>
- Toor, S., Ofori, G. (2009). Ethical leadership: Examining the relationships with full range leadership model, employee outcomes, and organizational culture. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 90 (4), 533. <https://doi:10.1007/s10551-009-0059-3>
- Treviño, L. K., Brown, M., & Hartman, L. P. (2003). A qualitative investigation of perceived executive ethical leadership: Perceptions from inside and outside the executive suite. *Human relations*, 56(1), 5-37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726703056001448>
- Turcotte, J. (2015). Chance York, Jacob Irving, Rosanne M. Scholl, and Raymond J. Pingree. 2015. News recommendations from social media opinion leaders: Effects on media trust and information seeking. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 20(5), 520-535. <https://doi:10.1111/jcc4.12127>
- Turos, E., & Shim, J. Y. (2015). *U.S. Patent No. 9,149,440*. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- Vassos, M., Nankervis, K., Skerry, T., & Lante, K. (2017). Can the job demand-control-(support) model predict disability support worker burnout and work engagement? *Journal of Intellectual & Developmental Disability*, 44(2), 139-149. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3109/13668250.2017.1310818>
- Veitch, J., Raymond, V., Farr, B., Farr, W., Graff, P., Vitale, S., & Wade, L. (2015). Parameter estimation for compact binaries with ground-based gravitational-wave observations using the LAL Inference software library. *Physical Review D*, 91(4), 042003.
- Wallace, J. C., Butts, M. M., Johnson, P. D., Stevens, F. G., & Smith, M. B. (2016). A multilevel model of employee innovation: Understanding the effects of regulatory focus, thriving, and employee involvement climate. *Journal of Management*, 42(4), 982–1004. doi:10.1177/0149206313506462
- Wang, Q., Qi, J., Yuan, Y., Xuan, Y., Han, P., Wan, Y., & Iwamoto, A. (2014). Bat origins of MERS-CoV supported by bat coronavirus HKU4 usage of human receptor CD26. *Cell host & microbe*, 16(3), 328-337. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chom.2014.08.009>

- Wombacher, J. C., & Felfe, J. (2017). Dual commitment in the organization: Effects of the interplay of team and organizational commitment on employee citizenship behavior, efficacy beliefs, and turnover intentions. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 102, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2017.05.004>
- Xu, P., Peng, G., Su, L., Gao, Y., Gao, L., & Li, D. (2018). Microplastic risk assessment in surface waters: A case study in the Changjiang Estuary, China. *Marine pollution bulletin*, 133, 647-654.
- Yaoa, T., Qiuc, Q., & Wei, Y. (2019). Retaining hotel employees as internal customers: Effect of organizational commitment on attitudinal and behavioral loyalty of employees. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 76, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2018.03.018>
- Yu, Q., Yen, D.A., Barnes, B.R., & Huang, Y.A. (2019). Enhancing firm performance through internal market orientation and employee organizational commitment. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30(6), 964-987. <https://doi:10.1080/09585192.2017.1380059>
- Zazou, H., Afanga, H., Akhouairi, S., Ouchtak, H., Addi, A. A., Akbour, R. A., & Hamdani, M. (2019). Treatment of textile industry wastewater by electrocoagulation coupled with electrochemical advanced oxidation process. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, 28, 214-221.
- Zhu, W., May, D. R., & Avolio, B. J. (2004). The impact of ethical leadership behavior on employee outcomes: The roles of psychological empowerment and authenticity. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 11(1), 16-26. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1071791904011>